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VRTN is functional during embryonic development.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of VRTN as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.